

Macroscopic and microscopic properties of fabric rubber composite

X.F. Yao*, Y.F. Dong

Applied Mechanics Laboratory, Department of Engineering Mechanics, Tsinghua University, Beijing, China. * Corresponding author (yxf@mail.tsinghua.edu.cn)

Abstract

Complex fabric rubber composites with high-performance and special material are widely used in aerospace due to their excellent mechanical and sealing properties, which consist of the matrix material with rubber and the reinforcement material with the fabric. Actually, there are different fabric structure on the inside and the surface for complex fabric rubber composite in aircraft door. The inner fabric is the reticulated fabric, which mainly plays the role of reinforcement. The surface fabric is densely distributed and mainly serves to resist abrasion. For the inner reticulated fabric rubber composites, the anisotropic hyperelastic model is used to characterize their mechanical properties. Because of the complex unit cell structure of woven composites, the mechanical properties of the dense surface fabric composites are investigated based on their mesoscopic structures.

Fig.1 Complex fabric rubber composite and fabric structures

Inner reticulated fabric rubber composite

Anisotropic hyperelastic model of the reticulated fabric rubber composite:

$$W = W_R + W_F + W_{int} = C_{10}(\theta)(I_1 - 3) + C_{01}(\theta)(I_2 - 3) + \frac{k_1(\theta)}{2k_2(\theta)} \sum_{j=4,6} \left[e^{k_2(\theta)(I_j - 1)^2} + \frac{k_2(\theta)}{4}(I_j - 1)^2 - 1 \right]$$

Fig.2 The uniaxial tensile experimental results of the inner reticulated fabric rubber composite

Surface fabric rubber composite

Fig.3 The physical map and geometrical model of surface fabric

Fig.4 The forming process of RVE for the surface fabric rubber composite

Mechanical property of the complex fabric rubber composite

Fig.5 The distribution of different material type of the complex fabric rubber composite

Fig.6 The numerical simulation results and experimental results of unit length load-displacement curves for the complex fabric rubber composite under different temperatures: (a) 25°C. (b) 50°C. (c) 70°C. (d) 90°C. (e) 110°C. (f) 130°C.